

Bagua Dharma Lectures 1 & 2

Fundamentals, Levels 1-3

Lecture 1 (am)

Laozi Sequence (Fibonacci)

0 - Wu

1 - Dao

1 - Shang Di (most High One)

2 - Yin & Yang

3 - Creative, Ren (Adam), Creation

5 - Fire, Earth, Metal, Water, Wood

8 - Heaven, Wind, River, Mountain,
Earth, Thunder, Lightning, Lake

What is Wu?

1/0-> Infinity

“the Oneness, divided by its emptiness, is infinite [and therefore unnamable and unknowable].”

This the Chinese called “Dao”

Shang Di was the prime observer of this phenomenon, and by splitting Wu, made Yin & Yang

Wu is the true emptiness

Which is NOT empty, and yet by definition it does not exist.

In other words Wu and Dao are NOT a duality... they are a Singularity. Wu is No Thing.

Wu is a 0 that when sliced makes a 0, ad infinitum.

From Wu come Dao and God

“First there was the 1, then the 2, then the 3, then the 10,000 things [everything]”

Literally God creates the world by trying to figure out the meaning of the One (Dao) that is of him and yet outside him* and the emptiness it comes from. Loneliness??

* This him is misleading, it is a pure YANG being but neither male nor female in the sexual sense. However, the CREATIVE is a pure yang over yang, unending power source. Typically male in description because yang moves and governs. But actually includes Creation as a part.

We are ALL a miniature Shang-Di
We want to name it (Dao) and yet it cannot
be named... we want to categorize its
evidence (Qi) yet cannot prove it, however
we know it exists by its movements.

the Way (Tao) and its Power (Te)

“We turn clay to make a vessel;
But it is on the space where there is nothing that the usefulness of the vessel depends.”

“The movement of the Tao
By contraries proceeds;
And weakness marks the course
Of Tao's mighty deeds.

All things under heaven sprang from It as existing (and named);
that existence sprang from It as non-existent (and not named).”

“Gravity is the root of lightness; stillness, the ruler of movement.”

What is Te?

Beyond today's subject, suffice it to say it is:

1. Morality/Righteousness
2. Inner containment (within chest)
3. Outward leverage and Force (weight)
4. Restrained, spontaneous Awesomeness

What is “Wu Wei”

Often mistranslated as “inaction”

>>Float like a leaf on the river of life...

>>how you end up going over waterfalls.

It is spontaneous non-action

(purpose-conceding) which leads to
mystical results (lit: fruits); it has a
“process”

Tian-Ren-Di = Heaven's Mandate

Tian Yi is the Mandate OF Heaven, or Heaven's Will (Fate). It is attained by knowing Tian-Ren-Di.

This Di is literally Earth, but for all intents and purposes means all of Creation

Ren=Adam=Mankind=Mind-born people

Tian is a FORCE from the Creative, like Grace;
Mo-di called it Universal Love (Agape)

道

道林人

壬午
時辰書

氣

**DIAGRAM 2 - Secrets Revealed
of Buddhist Swastika**

6 levels:

6 lines I Ching

6 stages of perfect

Wu Xing - 5 Phase Energies

4 Main Elements & Seasons
5th is Spirit

Chinese called them phases
Spirit belongs to Fire

Wood/Air, Earth, Water, and Metal/Soul
Earth=center/Mother; Metal=Father

8 Trigrams

$$2^3 = 8$$

Duality (Existence) “Taken to the Power” of the 3 planes creates the 8 dharma.

Dharma=binding law/contract (a lien on your Mandate of Heaven)

8 trigrams are like mathematical black boxes, calculating beyond reach.

Bagua Dharma

Heaven=Karma; Earth=Vibration/Quantum
Wind=Change/Flux/Evolution; Fire=Polarity
River=Relativity/Danger; Thunder=Rotation
Mountain=Conservation; Lake=Resonance
Resonance or Harmony informs Karma, and
hence Harmony is the secret of all existence

Yang (Heaven's Qi)
w/yin = Polarity
⑦

The 11th Realm - Oneness

(Dharma, God, Truth, Suchness, Nirvana, Wu, etc...)

Level of Resonance = Harmony
⑧

Yin
(Earth's Qi)

cause

Wind = Evolution
②

$$e^{i\theta} = \cos\theta + i \sin\theta \rightarrow \text{Rotation } \textcircled{6}$$

$$f \text{ (frequency)} = \text{Vibration } \textcircled{5}$$

$$E=mc^2 \text{ (conservation)} \Rightarrow c = \sqrt{v/m} \Rightarrow \text{Relativity } \textcircled{3}$$

Only light & Mind have
massless quanta or Complete
Universal View

①
Law of Karma →

effect

Bagun Dharma
-The 8 Universal Laws-

Comparative Vibrations of 10 Humanly Realms

Note the kindred nature of Realms 8-10, 5-7, 1-4, and also increasing Rotation and thus confusion / changing passions & emotions of the lower realms, with Hell (Misery) being impossibly difficult to have any chance out

$$\delta(x) = \begin{cases} +\infty, & x = 0 \\ 0, & x \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

At infinity (God), all is Void
When all is Void, things seem not void

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(x) dx = 1$$

The Integral Way uniting these truths
leads to Oneness.

**True North
aka "right"**

varying degrees of
rightness and
wrongness; relative
viewpoints associated
with mass-bound
objects and "limited
consciousness"

Healthy

Unhealthy

S
True south or "evil" aka wickedness leads also
to the Source via Reverting Yin
A non-pious life still winds up the same as a
pious life, though the outlook of the mind's
compass is very different

Why you must beware buying into the Zen-now/moment

The Mess of Dualistic Existence

Other Important Dualities:

Space & Time

Heavenly Father & Blessed Mother Nature

Moreover, even within the same Vibratory level, of course people are more often than not out-of-phase meaning they cannot understand one another's speech thoughts, and actions. See A-E

Phasing is not eliminated until the 11th Realm (death of ego/body - all 5 Shen) but the 10th & some 9th/8th realm can change phase at will/need hence the ability to get along with more people & see Sameness (Hexagram

Also, within this same vibratory level (Realm) or Amplitude in mathematics, some individuals operate at higher or lower frequencies relative to others in their Realm. This may be due to age, experience, culture/language, religion, or even psycho-somatic disease. Excepting the 10th Realm, we all have some form/degree of mental illness, so this explains why we can sense when others in our realm or lower realms are 'a bit off/crazy'.

The Spirit Plane

Karma is technically something you “carry” with you, so you can remember lessons.

The Spirit Plane or “reality” as we call it is a fluid potentiality-probability cloud, and our karma input is calculated (with a bit of jiggle too for spice), and out pops our existing experience aka results.

I think, therefore I am...

~Descartes

**... constantly tripping
over my own ego.**

~Karma

Brahmic-god
(up one level)
Heaven is the benevolent totality of force from "Beyond"

Tao forms a strata, like the canvas of a painting.

Tao (Dao) is the FLOW of the uni-multiverse
God is the Containment of IT ALL

The entire flow or process is called Heaven's Mandate (Tianming); it produces life. Including children and alchemical "spiritual embryos"

Taiji Pole

Shen

Blue arrows indicates polar attraction, red indicates normal magnetism of separating substances

> Holy Spirit

Qi/Prajna

Te (De) is concentration

Jing-Essence

The Golden Light emanates from "connection/concordance" of the fractal Brahma in the middle Dan Tian with the Bhagavan of the upper Dan Tian, which is empty above and letting God/Heaven fill the lower Dan Tian - to connect to Earth. This is the "mind of Tao" as a process rather than a state only. Concordance produces light.

Earth is the physical atoms and fields, forces, energy

Possible sources of "Mysterious Pass"

Random Alternate Universes

Chaotic changing density probability Field of uniform energy potential

Linear Universes

example: birth, life, then death... of anything

Parallel (Unpotentiated) Universes

Bounds of Vertical Universe

AKA, hyperdimensions
arguably also relativity related to
scaling up or down

Recursive Universe

Scaleable, Repeatable, Single Uni-multiverse

IOW

“You become what you think about”

~Buddha

You can be anything... given enough time,
Te, and good timing, anything is a
possibility.

So what is karma “control”?

Part 2 - Karma Control

You can't control it. End of Story?

>>two wheels on your karma

>one that crushes you

>one you can steer

You do not change the reality; it changes you and you design your destiny.

karmasutra

(n.) when fate fucks you in all sorts of creative ways

Karma

Cause and Effect exist simultaneously

Where people go wrong...

“I (myself) will do it.”

“If only I could just change it [the Data]”

>Law of Conservation is the VAULT

“I want to control yin & yang”

>Dualistic existence leads to ups & downs

“I want to be the judge and jury”

>Karma can “Reverse Bind” on you.

So what am I to do?

Three Stages in Shifu's Karma Alteration Rx

1) Seek Resonance

Technically this is all you need; albeit you'd have a lot of trial and error.

2) Re-program your egoic self (Human Mentality)

3) Seek the Mind of Tao (unity); alkalize!

Law of Resonance

Two things in resonance produce yang
(unity or growth)

Two things not in resonance produce yin
(separation or rot)

Law of Evolution states: “That which is not
growing is dying, nothing stays the same.”

>> Find a NICHE and dominate it.

This will do it

3 life examples? (your turn)

Jobs

Marriages

Friendships

Events

Projects

Hobbies

Changing Paradigms

To alter the Karma warp (weft is the 12 link chain of causation)... change not thoughts, habits, emotions, or beliefs alone, these are trunks and branches.

Change your PARADIGM to form a PRAXIS (unity of belief and action).

This is the root and even seeds. Takes TIME

How to find out paradigms

- >What you buy, wear, or espouse (check your FB feed)
- >Meditate deeply and ask into things about yourself
- >Observe current proclivities, most especially food and music, friends and movies, etc...

How to change them

First, do NOT fight your body directly... the egoic mind, once it has been in charge a long time is hard to overthrow.

Second, seek the Great Person(s)

Third, control and mistrust the “Traitor”

Fourth, trust the Mind of Tao - so seek Tao in everything... this leads to PRAXIS

Just like Revenge...

is a dish best served cold... changing your self is best done like putting a frog on the boil. Slowly, methodically, constantly, with effort.

This is the basic idea of Alchemy

“Changing your inner and outer reality to suit your Self.”

Let go and let God...

Although you can have a Vision and a plan, and a method and a willpower of your own, don't forget to let go and let it unfold as is Willed. For anyone who tries to overthrow Tian-Yi will risk losing both the thing they seek and even the Mandate of Life.

Caste changing?

Your caste is a starting point... a potential field that determines more or less your playground.

> You can try to become #1 in your caste (minor mastery)

> Or you can transcend all castes and become a “Superior” or Complete Being.

Destiny vs. Fate

Fate is written after the Karma enters back into the VAULT. Fate means after you died. Destiny is that which you are potentially best able to become in a chosen data stream (like a profession)... but few reach it.

Luck is based on your karmic birth factors.

Do not beat your head against Fate or Luck

It is pointless to work with these.

Work with your destiny and with the 1 law you have control over: your vibration. Your vibe brings you resonance or disharmony... this you can control. This is how you “steer”.

Do not try to overthrow your being's bounds: what are they??

What is Alchemy?

- >Alkalize: to change or alter
- >Acidify: to remove/reduce
- >Fusion: to compress
- >Fission: to disperse
- >Purification and changing comes from constant entry of purified Qi, and expulsion of Xie (toxic) Qi

What is the Dark Side?

False Yin, it is the creeping process of Rot Sneaks up on us as we age, as we do not pay attention. Difficult to see as it is without...

Distraction: that which distorts our Gaze
Oblivion (psychic-dampness): that which lulls us and dulls us.

Repulsing Yin

All people have true YIN and YANG;
repulsing yin is a matter of promoting Yang Qi (Zhen, Zheng, Yuan, Wei, Shen) and nourishing true YIN (Jing, Hun, fluids)
Use YIN to buffer against yin; use Yang only when it is safe to “advance the fire”

Advancing Fire

Quite literally “stoking the bellows” aka breathing in the abdomen... sending Qi down into the feet.

Certain days it is unsafe, and certain times, but mostly there is always a way.

Protect Illumination, do not use it up.

Everything is a substance

All things physical and metaphysical (yes even numbers and sounds) are frequency adjusting. The key is to control your frequency modulators and not let any of them get too used; avoid toxic ones. (ex: Death Metal; hatred; meth, etc...)

Using a substance requires Qi and Jing

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compass is very different

Double Alchemy

Do be do be do...

This means also root head root head root...

This means also sin purify sin purify sin...

This means also good food, bad, good,
bad...

But each iteration, less egregious in
violation of Dharma, hence alkalizing

HEAVEN (the Force of Yang)
Holy Spirit or Ether, Tao

Taiji Pole
A toroidal vortex (not depicted)

2 lines symbolize inexhaustibility of TAO

LING SHU
= Mysterious Pivot

The switch between heaven oriented and earthly oriented mind is a matter of the soul-atom's focus. It is kind of about morality, but in either choice, the result is that you can perform Alchemy, and Operate the Fire, because the yellow court is the blossom between the solar plexus and the Christ (chest) chakra, aka Golden Flower
When you switch, you will feel a 'snap.'
That snap is referred to in the Sutras as literal snapping, now you know why.

EARTH
(the strata of Creation), receptivity

FIRE
(spirit-fire)
heart-mind

GOLDEN FLOWER
aka Christ chakra or Mind of Tao
aka Buddha-mind
it is the flower of the soul-atom
It is recharged via HEAVEN force

Mysterious Pivot- crossing of Taiji pole (center), and midpoints of body (center of center)

True Yin, aka spiritual embryo,
aka Gold Pill
location not depicted here, just containment in the HEAVEN buried from breath-work and spiritual-gazing; whatever tehcniques used.

WATER
Ming-men
water-fire
sexual energy

Some might mistakenly think the WATER is drained of Yang, but that is only if the Ling Shu is not performed. If the person has the red arrow coming down, it fills all YIN, and hence K'AN turns to TUI - Joy, which is also water (lake)

EARTH over HEAVEN
= #11 Tranquility
(see Sun diagram)

SUN SUBSURFACE

Internal structure:
Inner core
Radiative zone
Convection zone

11. Tranquility - Earth over Heaven (aka matter over energy)

Crushing weight

Uplifting pressure

The sun "ignites" continually because its size has "critical mass" which means the gravity of the matter is so great it causes thermonuclear fusion. In fusion, two atoms are forced together, creating a new atom in a lower energetic state. This means that un-needed energy is "thrown off" as a photon. The sun is so large, and the matter so much it takes photons at the center of the sun up to 100,000 years on average just to escape the sun! This is extreme "cultivation;" Furthermore, the sun lives 10 billion years or so in this state, then it grows massive, explodes, shedding its excess "impurities"; shrinks down and becomes a white dwarf. It then lives 10x as long or 100 billion years!

This is a true alchemical furnace/meditation master. This is because it achieves Tranquility.

Notice the Sun also has 6 layers, just as the human body does. Believe it or not, the Corona is hotter than the Chromosphere, because very hot jets of energy flow out from the Convection Zone below, venting heat. These are like pores on the body, hence the Qi body of a human is hotter than the skin, and if it is not present, then the skin is easily chilled. In the human body the "convection zone" is the Yangming, which has the most Qi & blood. Hence it translates as Yang Brightness. Those who understand this will be able to perceive immediately the dynamics of longevity. At its basis, this is it. Many changes and methods exist to enable the practitioner to attain this. But the ones that work all have this as their guiding/basic principle; it is just physics.

7 chakras

7 colors

7 bodily

sense

rotating

Tesla coil?

Further reading

Alchemy Questions

- >Is sexual alchemy best? Not for most people.
- >Is it the only way? No.
- >Is Alchemy only about the outside? No.
- >Is Alchemy easy? Yes and of course, no.
- >How can I get started? (take notes now)
- >Can it be dangerous? Absolutely.

Unsaid Rules of Alchemy

Once you start you must continue or you lose it all... feels like punishment.

Must be willing to sacrifice...

Jing

Qi

Objects

Negative Relationships

What IS Qi?

Ling-shu (mysterious pivot) generated.
A generator is alternating rotational energy... so Qi is the force generated by life's movements of yin and yang within each... beyond measurement but visible.
All things are Qi, but Qi we mean to speak of is a life-force... Vitality... the Living Force

Qi production

Yuan - Original/inborn

Zhen - True

Zeng - Chest/ancestral

Zheng - Upright/Correct

Jing - Essence

Wei - Defense (volumetric)

Ying - Nutritive/plasma

12 channels and Six Divisions and 5 Elements

Fire-->Earth-->Metal/Ether-->Water-->Wood-->Fire

Water*~*Fire*~*Metal*~*Wood*~*Earth*~*Water

Taiyin
(greatest yin)

Yangming
(yang brightest)

Shaoyin
(lesser yin)

Taiyang
(greatest yang)

Jueyin
(reverting yin)

Shaoyang
(middle yang)

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www.bluelotushealth.com

The TCM Qi Clock & Diurnal Physiological Activity.

By: Paul Hysen PhD. © 2013

FIVE ELEMENTS

CYCLES OF GENERATION AND CONTROL

CYCLES OF IMBALANCE

Please note: All physiological function times are approximate.

Shen & Yi & Zhi

Shen = spirit

Shen also is the affect/a flower of Yi

Yi is mind/intellect

Yi -> Po = Human Mind

Yi -> Hun = Mind of Tao

Zhi = will/memory

Hun & Po

Hun = ethereal soul

Hun + shen = subconscious (lower CNS)

Po = corporeal soul (a physical presence)

[technically there are 7 Po and 5 Hun]

Hun + Po = unconscious (PNS/ENS/ANS)

Liver Qi -> SNS || PsNS rel. Spleen Qi

SNS also covered by Chong -> HT -> chakra

Why do we self-destruct?

Tranquility is Earth over Heaven

Obstruction is Heaven over Earth

You are in samsara:: Obstruction.

#2, body is of earth (clay), soul is of heaven, so they are attracted to doing things which “separate yin and yang”

If po don't find a physical way, mind will.

True Longevity

After restoring the KI channel and other obstructions removed...

Must reverse the 5 Element hyper-flow

“Reversing the Normal Path of Creation.”

to “take over” and “become a peer with

Tian.” Does not mean a god, but an

Immortal (Hsien)

Immortality = Truth of Birthlessness

You are not born, you do not die.

You are infinitely aged.

You are connected, a parcel of the Divine

You are we, we are One.

You are deserving of all forgiveness.

It comes from within your Self. Self=Lord

Thus the golden flower/heart chakra is the

Christ Mind/Buddha Mind/Mind of Tao

BUT...

After Tian Gui (Heaven's Water) flows... the Stripping Away (Original Sin) process starts... and you age and unless you seek Restoration you will lose the Mandate too early to become a realized Hsien. (enlightened)... and have to start over and over again.

SACRED ACLEHMY

-SPIRITUAL,
-SEXUAL,
-MENTAL,
-PHYSICAL

Turn This Into

This

Function of Marriage

Marriage is a biological anathema... even paired birds have affairs, esp. the females. Human Marriage is a gift designed to lead to inner peace. It is therefore HARD to practice.

External yin/yang == internal.

Husband/Wife block == separation yin/yang

False

True

True

False

Domineering
Demanding
Angry/short fused
Anxious/hasty
Worry
Judgmental

(failure to set vibration)

Listens to partner
Open to ideas
Attentive to others' needs
Receptive to Tianming
Short/concise actions
Stillness in body, mind, and spirit

(not ruminating)

Not easily distracted
Controls space and manages her time
Feels and acts empowered
Does not try to thieve essence from man

(harmonious balance)

life's gifts never enough
judgmental and critical
feeling lack in mind
pensive
afraid
short-tempered

(loss of stillness)

Excessive desires "fetch the moon" or
"pie in the sky"
high expectations
sexually frustrated

increased beyond normal ambitions
unaware of cyclic changes in biology
addictions

(following Wu xing cycle to early death)

*note not starts in men from bottom up

Listens to "gut" - knows Right
Active, spontaneous
Virtuous deeds
Regulating the inside and the
outside
Harmonizing force
Controlling appetites

Still within
Listens well, and understands well
Considerate of fragile male ego
Not arguing point-by-point; which excites
male ego to more false yang
Attentive to male needs, husband before
children, father before all

henpecking
hesitant
does not exert power
does not dissuade false yin from
external sources
out of sync vibrationally with
male/yang force
assumptions made
impatient for change

*When either side absent, borrow from "other" to regulate children
*Read as "do this->result"
*#11 Tranquility forms a mirror with each other's feet meeting
*can be applied hetero/homosexual, all vibrational information
*Created by Sf. Ramon and Arwen Careaga co-mutually to describe the effects of polar Human Mentality activity
-When both people are True, this is Home Mind-of-Tao-

Family Alchemy

Each trigram belongs to a member of family.

By fulfilling the niche, one “consummates” the family’s position and holds the Mandate in place. This is for curing curses and reversing Dissolution.

VERY HARD PRACTICE

Alchemy of Life

External alchemy is divided into yin and yang (yin being laboratory alchemy or ingesting substances to alter self; triple-herbalism [drugs, herbs, and neuro])
Yang is the alteration of outside karmic influences. Mostly about letting go of old karma to take in new... but...

There is also a process.

Secrets to this are in the I ching/Taoist
Not about memorization or about coins
About “Synchronicity”

This is where Bing Fa and Confucian studies
are a MUST

Bing Fa & Propriety

Bing Fa are strategems and methods of war
Not about conflict but winning BEFORE
conflict arises

Propriety has 3 great weapons for bing fa
all work because of souls and Dharma

1) Sincerity, 2) Benevolence, 3)

Righteousness ---> all display Magnanimous
Might (Awesomeness)

Bign Fa and the Mandate

If you use/overuse Bing Fa, and even Propriety... you run the risk of losing your Elixir in anything.

eg. tattling at a job (whistleblowing)

eg. using a PI to out a suspected affair

Before heading to war, check yourself, Self, flank, do research, and prepare to lose Qi and Jing... is it worth it??

Bing Fa Musts

Art of War = 101, Musashi's 5 Rings=102

Taigong's 6 Secret Teachings, Mozi = 201

Sun Bin, Wuzi, 36 strategems = 202

Romance of the 3 Kingdoms = Master's

Zhuge Liang's Bing Fa & Guiguzi = PhD

You must temper the “Dragon”

Hidden Dragon

Becoming a dragon is dangerous. Both to self and others.

<divulge stories>

All about Use of Illumination and Purpose

You must learn to sheathe the weaponry

Tongue, fingers, mind.

Use the Dharma to transform them

A Dragon Takes Flight

To take flight, a dragon must cocoon and molt. Then spread wings and practice.

Not without some battle scars.

Return to the Egg... not the birth egg.

Alchemy is again the key. Fusion, not

fission... not black holes, not toxic

radiation. Return to before the Duality

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(up one level)
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Your Intellect's Choice

Ego, aka "The Human Mentality"
aka "Acquired Conditioning"
aka the "Guest"

Restoring the Elixir, aka
"Gold Pill" aka Original Self
--Alchemy--

Your Soul's Choice

Original Mind, aka "Mind of Tao"
aka "Christ/Krishna/Buddha Conscious"
aka the "Host"

Delusional State

"I am me, alone, individual. I have a brain that runs my body. The Mind is a function of the brain. It is all that matters. Everything is happenstance and purely unimportant. If I prolong my body forever, I will live forever."
aka the "Being of Form"

--Free Will--
"Vibrational
Attunement"

Seeker/Arhat State

"I am that I AM, coherent, dependent on all creation and causality. The Mind is all that matters, I have a soul with a body. I live forever. Everything that happens is fated and according to a plan. I live forever in a state of the Matrix (void), in suspended animation, a perpetual dream.
aka the "Being of Formlessness"

the Mysterious Pass

Your Avatar

Your soul-atom

The Truth beyond truths is you first make the "Right" choice, but then you see it also as a permanent delusion, and follow it back to the source, and you see your Self for what it is. Hollow and yet Being; full of non-Being, beyond duality, older than Heaven and Earth (Creation), without source except with the One (Tao or true God); forever and ever. Submitting to it, you fall into step with it, understanding it, and you escape the dream - you see the Uni-multiverse. Non-formists will say there is nothing at the source, they are just addicts.

***Please note: your Avatar lives only once, hence the belief in one life is true; your soul-atom lives forever, hence re-incarnation is also true. Solve the math equation, and the Data Matrix is solved.**

further reading

Nei Yeh

Tao Te Ching & Chuang Tzu

Secret of the Golden Flower

Yojokun (Yang Shen)

Desiderata

shifucareaga.com

www.resonance.is

THANK YOU

for being you.